

Improving the energy efficiency of two-speed motors through the use of new pole-switched windings

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the design and manufacturing of two-speed asynchronous motors with pole-changing windings. The need for developing two-speed motors with a single pole-changing winding is justified from the standpoint of energy and resource efficiency, as well as improved starting performance of high-power electric drives. An analysis of existing pole-changing winding designs is presented, highlighting their practical limitations in industrial applications. A new pole-changing winding with a 4/2 pole ratio and 48 stator slots was developed using the discrete spatial functions method based on star-delta-double star configurations. The electromagnetic characteristics of the proposed winding were analyzed. Based on this design, a new 4A200L8/4U3 two-speed motor was manufactured and tested under production conditions at the energy motors plant. Experimental results show that at $p_1 = 4$ pole pairs the motor delivers $P_2 = 20$ kW with efficiency $\eta = 87\%$, $\cos \varphi = 0.82$, $I_1 = 43$ A at slip $s = 2.35\%$, while at $p_2 = 2$ pole pairs it develops $P_2 = 36$ kW with efficiency $\eta = 91.5\%$, $\cos \varphi = 0.906$, $I_1 = 66$ A at slip $s = 1.5$. The results confirm more efficient utilization of the active magnetic core at lower polarity and demonstrate the feasibility of implementing such motors for energy-saving applications in heavy-duty drives requiring two equivalent operating speeds.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, along with frequency control, electric drives with two-speed motors (DD) have become widespread. These drives have a number of advantages, such as low cost, no additional devices, and ease of control and operation, as well as high efficiency in terms of energy savings with less stringent requirements [1]. DDs with pole ratios of 1/2, 1/3, 1/4, 1/5, and 1/6 are widely used in numerous lifting and transport mechanisms (hoists, elevator installations), metalworking machines (lathes, milling machines, grinding machines), and agricultural machinery (conveyors, screw conveyors, crushers, and AVM-type drying units). In most cases, these mechanisms operate under heavy loads and have a large number of starts (up to 200 per hour).

DD motors with pole ratios of 2/3, 3/4, 4/5, and 5/6 can be used in mechanisms with fan loads (pumps, fans, and centrifugal compressors), in the mining and processing industry (conveyors, feeders, crushers, mills), and in agricultural machinery (separators, drum mills, screening machines). DDs of a particular ratio are used to perform the technological process by the equipment where they are installed, the operating mode of which is determined by many independent factors: climatic and weather conditions, the technological process of industrial enterprises, and the operating mode of organizations, which are usually characterized by work schedules or a cycle diagram for performing a single process.

Two-speed asynchronous motors can also be used to facilitate the start-up of electric motors in harsh conditions [2], [3]. Two-speed asynchronous motors provide a quick start, in which the initial acceleration is carried out at low speed, and then the electric motor switches to high speed [4]. Many of the existing two-speed motors have two or more separate windings on the stator, which requires higher costs than single-winding motors – 30–40% for electrical steel and 40–50% for winding copper, with a corresponding increase in labor intensity. In addition, the efficiency and $\cos\phi$ of the motor are reduced by an average of 10–15%.

The use of a single pole-changing winding (PCW) with two groups of terminals for each pole allows for more efficient use of the active part of the machine, saves on winding copper and insulating materials, improves energy performance, and makes it possible to bring the mass and size of a two-speed motor closer to those of conventional single-speed asynchronous motors [2]. Windings obtained on the basis of pole-amplitude modulation (PAM) and phase modulation (PM) methods can have significant asymmetry, which can be eliminated by using the summarization method leads to an increase in the number of stator slots, which is not always acceptable. In addition, in many cases, the selectivity of the resulting windings and the values of their winding coefficients are insufficient.

Despite a significant number of scientific works and substantial development of methods for constructing PAMs over the past decades, attempts at their practical application have been successful only in isolated cases due to the large number of output terminals, switching contacts, deteriorated electromagnetic properties, and complex manufacturing technology associated with the production of coils of different types and with different pitches.

This clearly demonstrates the advisability of continuing the search for ways to obtain simple and reliable PCW circuits that meet the requirements of electrical engineering. The current tasks in this area are to minimize the number of terminals and switching contacts, as well as to coordinate magnetic induction values, high technological efficiency, and improved electromagnetic properties. With increasing demands on the quality of finished materials, there is a need to create more advanced motor designs. In these industries, the most important factor is not only high productivity and quality of output, but also high energy efficiency of equipment, which is becoming critically important given rising energy costs and the need to reduce carbon emissions [2].

A distinctive feature of all types of engines is that they are started under difficult conditions, which is one of the significant technical problems. Under the conditions of traditional relay-contactor circuits [2], [3] for controlling electric drives, the mixers are started by repeatedly turning on and off the asynchronous motor, which leads to increased inertia and high resistance moments during start-up. These factors, as shown in [1], require significant energy consumption for startup and can lead to increased wear of equipment, which influences its durability and reliability. This leads to accelerated wear of the mechanical gears and the motor itself and decreases its service life. Two-speed asynchronous motors can also be used to make it easier to start electric motors in demanding conditions. Two-speed asynchronous motors ensure a dry start, wherein the initial acceleration takes place at low speed, and then the electric motor switches to high speed.

Many existing two-speed motors have two or more separate windings on the stator, which impairs their weight, size and power characteristics. The application of a single pole-switched winding in two-speed motors, which has two groups of terminals for each pole, enables one to use the active part of the machine more efficiently, save winding copper and insulating materials, raise energy performance, and makes it possible to advance a two-speed motor in terms of weight and size to conventional serial single-speed asynchronous motors.

Many of the developed circuits of pole-switched windings fail to find practical use due to the large number of terminal ends, switching contacts, degraded electromagnetic properties, as well as complex manufacturing technology associated with coils with various turns and pitch [5]-[13]. Research in the field of asynchronous electric drives and pole-changing windings covers a wide range of tasks: from improving energy efficiency to optimizing the design parameters of machines. Shamsutdinov [1] explained considers ways to modernize the asynchronous drive of ball mills, while [2] systematically develop the concept of pole-changing windings for lifting, transport, and turbomachinery, proposing new winding designs with a close and variable pole ratio. Parallel studies [8], [12]-[15] confirm that the use of optimized pole-changing circuits and the 3/Y-3/Y method improves electromagnetic characteristics, reduces torque ripple, and increases motor stability in transient modes.

An important contribution to motor diagnostics and protection was made by [1], [10], [16], [17], which proposed sensor less control methods, protective devices without current transformers, and diagnostic algorithms using neural networks and search windings. Works [18]-[21] are aimed at improving the energy

efficiency of electric drives in oilfield, railway, and industrial installations, including the automation of tests to optimize machine characteristics. Research on multipole and high-speed synchronous motors with permanent magnets has undergone significant development. [7], [22]-[25] demonstrate the influence of the number of slots, coil pitch, and pole shape on the losses, torque, and thermal regime of high-speed machines. The works in [26], [27] investigate specific problems of suspended and contactless motors, as well as the suppression of unbalanced magnetic forces.

Additional areas include loss simulation, optimization of two-pole motor characteristics and methods for increasing the thermodynamic efficiency of electrical systems [28]-[30]. Finally, proposed efficiency maps for wide load ranges, which allow for improving the economic efficiency of asynchronous machines. Current research focuses on improving pole-changing, multi-speed, and high-speed motors, improving their electromagnetic properties, energy efficiency, and reliability. Despite significant progress, there is still a need for more accurate models of electromagnetic processes, unified methods for designing windings, and the integration of analytical methods with numerical modeling, especially when motors are operating in heavy and dynamic modes.

All the presented studies stress the importance of optimizing the design and control characteristics of motors to increase their energy efficiency. The use of new pole-switched windings is one of the key areas for improving the performance of two-speed motors, which allows for a significant reduction in energy losses and increased productivity. The aim of this work is to develop new pole-changing winding schemes and, based on them, to design two-speed motors with improved energy characteristics. The scientific novelty of the work consists of the development of a new pole-changing winding scheme based on the basic “Y- Δ /YY” scheme with a pole ratio of 8/4 at 48 stator slots, which has improved electromagnetic characteristics and consistency of magnetic inductions in the air gap of the machine.

2. METHOD

A new method called “discrete spatial functions” (DSF) was proposed for constructing PCW, based on the joint consideration of current distributions of two or more conventional windings, expressed as discrete spatial functions. The discrete element of the DSF winding is the state of the conductor. This name is assigned to the coil side of the winding with one conventional conductor belonging to one of the winding phases and designated identically with this phase. For example, states a, b, c are conventional conductors with unit currents (or electromotive force (EMF)) in the positive direction in the slots (i.e., “away from us”), belonging to phases A, B, C. The minus sign in front of a, b, and c corresponds to conductors with unit currents (or EMF) in the negative direction in the slots (i.e., “towards us”).

The construction of PCW is based on special basic circuits (BC) that have two groups of terminals, and when switching the power supply from one group of terminals to another, the number of pole pairs changes (in relation to one group of terminals, they are $2p_1$ -pole, and in relation to the other, they are $2p_2$ -pole). When constructing a PCW based on this method using BC “Y/YY”, it is possible to consider both $m-2m$ -zone and $2m-2m$ -zone windings together, and when using BC “YYY/YYY”, $m-m$ -zone or $2m-2m$ -zone windings can be considered together, but the joint consideration of $2m-2m$ -zone windings often leads to the use of the YYY/YYYYYYY busbar [1], [2].

The windings obtained by this method are as close as possible in their electromagnetic and technological properties to normal windings. Let us consider the process of constructing a pole-changing winding with a pole ratio of 8/4 with 48 stator slots. In this case, the current distribution of $m-2m$ -zone windings is considered. The pole-changing winding is constructed on the basis of the Y- Δ /YY connection (see Figure 1), which has two groups of terminals, with terminals A, B, C for $2p_1 = 4$ and terminals D, E, F for $2p_2 = 8$ on the pole side [31], [32].

As the initial winding, we will take an m -zone winding with $p_2 = 4$, and with the number of slots per pole and phase $q_2 = 4$, and as the standard winding, we will take a normal $2m$ -zone winding with $p_1 = 2$ and $q_1 = 4$. We record the DSF of the lower layer of each winding under each other, then the correlation of the rows will be as shown in Table 1. The resulting circuit of a pole-switched winding is a “Dahlander” circuit [2], [22], [23], [31]. To improve electromagnetic properties, match inductions in the air gap, and symmetry, it is advisable to use additional branches.

The number of coils placed in additional branches may be 17-50% of the total number. Those coils that are ineffective in creating the total EMF of the phase are placed in additional branches. The coils of the additional branches are distributed with the condition of mutual compensation, because when a power source is connected from the pole side, where there are no additional branches, EMFs are induced in them, which contribute to the creation of equalizing currents. The underlined coils shown in Table 1 can be brought-out into additional branches [24]. Record the DSF of the winding from the side of both poles, considering the coils brought out into additional branches (see Tables 2 and 3).

Figure 1. Basic “Y-Δ/YY” diagram

Table 1. DSF of the lower winding layer

Stator slot	Lower-layer DSF (+/-)	Stator slot	Lower-Layer DSF (+/-)
1	a	26	a
2	a	27	a
3	a	28	a
4	a	29	c
5	c	30	c
6	c	31	c
7	c	32	c
8	c	33	b
9	b	34	b
10	b	35	b
11	b	36	b
12	b	37	a
13	a	38	a
14	a	39	a
15	a	40	a
16	a	41	c
17	c	42	c
18	c	43	c
19	c	44	c
20	c	45	b
21	b	46	b
22	b	47	b
23	b	48	b
24	b	2p	8
25	a	4	4

Table 2. DSF of pole-switched winding on minor polarity

Stator slots	Lower-layer DSF (+/-)	Stator slots	Lower-layer DSF (+/-)
1	-c	26	a
2	a	27	b
3	b	28	b
4	b	29	b
5	b	30	-c
6	-c	31	-c
7	-a	32	-a
8	-a	33	-a
9	-a	34	b
10	b	35	c
11	c	36	c
12	c	37	c
13	c	38	-a
14	-a	39	-a
15	-b	40	-b
16	-b	41	-b
17	-b	42	c
18	c	43	c
19	a	44	a
20	a	45	a
21	a	46	-b
22	-b	47	-b
23	-c	48	-c
24	-c	2p	4
25	-c	a	4

Table 3. DSF of pole-switched winding on greater polarity

Stator slots	Lower-layer DSF (+/-)	Stator slots	Lower-layer DSF (+/-)
1	a	26	a
2	a	27	a
3	a	28	-b
4	-b	29	c
5	c	30	c
6	c	31	c
7	c	32	-a
8	-a	33	b
9	b	34	b
10	b	35	b
11	b	36	-c
12	-c	37	a
13	a	38	a
14	a	39	a
15	a	40	-b
16	-b	41	c
17	c	42	c
18	c	43	c
19	c	44	-a
20	-a	45	b
21	b	46	b
22	b	47	b
23	b	48	-c
24	-c	2p	8
25	a	-c	8

Based on the obtained DSF, we draw up a diagram of the PSW connections: the diagram of the PSW connections is drawn up taking into account the property of the BC (in half of the coils the sign changes, see Table 4) and, considering the first and third rows, based on the state of the signs, the branch corresponding to a particular coil number is determined. The magnetizing force curves (see Figure 2) generated by the PCW on both poles are close to a sine wave, and the winding has fairly high winding coefficients, with $k_1 = 0.691$ on the $2p_1 = 4$ pole side and on the side of $2p_2 = 8$, $k_2 = 0.876$. The winding is completely symmetrical with respect to the power source.

Table 4. Coil grouping in the branch of the BC winding

Coil No.								
A1	B1	C1	A2	B2	C2	A3	B3	C3
4,	12,	8,	13,	21,	5,	1,	9,	17,
16,	24,	20,	14,	22,	6,	2,	10,	18,
28,	36,	32,	15,	23,	7,	3,	11,	19,
40	48	44	37,	45,	29,	25,	33,	41,
			38,	46,	30,	26,	34,	42,
			39	47	31	27	35	43

Figure 2. Pictures of magnetizing forces: (a) from the side $2p = 4$ and (b) from the side $2p = 8$

The coils of each branch (A1...C3) are connected in series according to the grouping in Table 4. The polarity of each subsequent coil is determined by the signs of the DSF (rows 1 and 3). When the signs of adjacent coils match, a matched series connection (end–start) is established. When the sign changes, the coil is connected in reverse (the terminals are flipped), ensuring the desired direction of the resulting magnetomotive force of the branch, taking into account the BC property (sign change in half of the coils).

It is known that in the air gap of an electric machine, along with the fundamental harmonic field, there is also a whole range of higher harmonic fields [31], [32]. The occurrence of higher harmonics is associated with the impossibility of distributing the linear load in space in a strictly sinusoidal manner. The winding is divided into a limited number of zones, as a result of which the shape only approximates a sine wave to a certain degree. This is the reason for the appearance of higher harmonics, whose amplitude decreases with increasing order. Tables 5 and 6 show the results of electromagnetic analysis.

Table 5. Results of electromagnetic analysis on side $2p_1 = 4$

v	F _{nm}	K_W	F _{nm} taking into account K_W	F _{nm} /F Σ %, taking into account K_W
1	3.959	0.691	2.736	96.43%
3	0.000	0.569	0.000	0.00%
5	0.082	0.358	0.029	1.03%
7	0.093	0.228	0.021	0.75%
9	0.000	0.098	0.000	0.00%
11	0.114	0.220	0.025	0.89%
13	0.097	0.220	0.021	0.75%
15	0.000	0.098	0.000	0.00%
17	0.038	0.114	0.004	0.15%

Table 6. Results of electromagnetic analysis on side $2p_2 = 8$

v	F _{nm}	K_W	F _{nm} taking into account K_W	F _{nm} /F Σ %, taking into account K_W
1	4.125	0.877	3.619	95.06%
3	0.000	0.250	0.000	0.00%
5	0.221	0.108	0.024	0.63%
7	0.158	0.224	0.035	0.93%
9	0.000	0.250	0.000	0.00%
11	0.075	0.877	0.066	1.73%
13	0.063	0.877	0.056	1.46%
15	0.000	0.250	0.000	0.00%
17	0.065	0.108	0.007	0.19%

As can be seen from Tables 5 and 6, as well as Figure 3, the value of the first harmonic is relatively large, and with side $2p_1 = 4$ is equal to 96.43%, and side $2p_2 = 8$ is equal to 95.06%; there are no even harmonics on side $2p^2 = 8$. The shape of the Gorges diagrams is close to a circle on both pole sides (see Figure 4),

the value of the differential dispersion coefficients is minimal, with $\sigma_0 = 2.0\%$ on the $2p_1 = 4$ side and $\sigma_0 = 1.4\%$ on the $2p_2 = 8$ side.

Figure 5 shows the electrical circuit diagram of the proposed three-phase pole-switched winding with a pole ratio of 8/4. The winding coils are grouped in a delta circuit with additional branches - a double star, wherein coils with serial numbers 4, 16 are connected in series in part A_{1,1}, coils with serial numbers 14, 20 are connected in series in part A_{1,2}, coils with serial numbers 12, 24 are connected in series in part B_{1,1}, coils with serial numbers 36, 48 are connected in series in part B_{1,2}, coils with serial numbers 8, 20 are connected in series in part C_{1,1}, coils with serial numbers 32, 44 are connected in series in part C_{1,2}, coils with serial numbers 13, 14, 15, 37, 38, 39 are connected in series in part A₂, coils with serial numbers 1, 2, 3, 25, 26, 27 are connected in series in part A₃, coils with serial numbers 21, 22, 23, 45, 46, 47 are connected in series in part B₂, coils with serial numbers 9, 10, 11, 33, 34, 35 are connected in series in part B₃, coils with serial numbers 5, 6, 7, 29, 30, 31 are connected in series in part C₂, coils with serial numbers 17, 18, 19, 41, 42, 43 are connected in series in part C₃.

Figure 3. Histogram of harmonics: (a) from the side $2p = 4$ and (b) from the side $2p = 8$

Figure 4. Görges diagrams: (a) from the side $2p = 4$ and (b) from the side $2p = 8$

Figure 5. Electrical diagram of the proposed three-phase pole-switched winding with a pole ratio of 8/4

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the developed PCW diagram using the ANSYS Maxwell program, a two-speed motor was designed, and according to the calculation data at energy motors, an experimental model of a new two-speed motor with a pole ratio of 8/4 was manufactured based on the magnetic circuit of a serial machine of type 4A2. Energy motors, an experimental model of a new two-speed motor with a pole ratio of 8/4 was manufactured based on the magnetic circuit of a serial machine of the 4A200L4UZ type with a stator slot number $Z_1 = 48$ and a rotor slot number $Z_2 = 38$, and a stator package length $l_s = 215$ mm. The winding is made with the same number of conductors in each slot $w_n=18$ with enamel-coated winding wire (ECWW) wire $\phi = 1.18$ mm. The number of consecutive turns in phase with the number of pole pairs $p_1 = 2$ is $w_2 = 72$, and with the number of pole pairs $p_2 = 4$ is $w_4 = 108$. This ensures a ratio of induction in the air gap of the motor with this winding $B_{\delta 8}/B_{\delta 4} = 1.15$.

To analyze the operation of the designed motor, an accurate mathematical description of the electromagnetic processes occurring in it is required. To do this, we will use the well-known Park-Clark transformations, in which the three-phase coordinate system (a, b, c) is transformed into an equivalent two-axis system (α, β): For example, in a three-phase system, instantaneous phase voltages can be expressed as sinusoidal functions (1) of time:

$$\begin{cases} u_a(t) = U_m \cos \omega t \\ u_b(t) = U_m \cos(\omega t - 2\pi/3), \\ u_c(t) = U_m \cos(\omega t + 2\pi/3) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where, U_m is the maximum phase voltage, ω is the angular frequency.

To convert to an equivalent two-axis conversion, this conversion is expressed as (2).

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_\alpha \\ u_\beta \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_a \\ u_b \\ u_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Next, the stationary $\alpha\beta$ components are transformed into a rotating coordinate system as (3).

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_d \\ u_q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\theta & \sin\theta \\ -\sin\theta & \cos\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_\alpha \\ u_\beta \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Where $\theta = \omega t$ is the electrical angle showing how much the rotating coordinate system (dq -axis) has rotated during time t .

As a result, sinusoidal voltages in the abc system are converted into constant values in the d -system under steady-state symmetric conditions. To analyze the operation of the motor, it is necessary to create a dynamic model of the machine in the form of state equations, where flux linkages are considered as the main variables:

– Stator flux linkage equations in the dq axes

$$\begin{cases} F_{ds} = \omega_b \psi_{ds} = X_{ls} i_{ds} + X_m (i_{ds} + i_{dr}) \\ F_{qs} = \omega_b \psi_{qs} = X_{ls} i_{qs} + X_m (i_{qs} + i_{qr}) \end{cases}$$

– Rotor flux linkage equations in the dq axes

$$\begin{cases} F_{dr} = \omega_b \psi_{dr} = X_{lr} i_{dr} + X_m (i_{ds} + i_{dr}) \\ F_{qr} = \omega_b \psi_{qr} = X_{lr} i_{qr} + X_m (i_{qs} + i_{qr}) \end{cases}$$

– Equations of magnetizing flux links in axes dq

$$\begin{cases} F_{dm} = \omega_b \psi_{dm} = X_m (i_{ds} + i_{dr}) \\ F_{qm} = \omega_b \psi_{qm} = X_m (i_{qs} + i_{qr}) \end{cases}$$

Where ω_b is the base electrical circular frequency of the machine, $X_{ls} = \omega_b L_{ls}$, $X_{lr} = \omega_b L_{lr}$, and $X_m = \omega_b L_m$.

When analyzing electromagnetic and electromechanical processes, it is necessary to perform a large number of mathematical calculations, which is possible using computer technology. Therefore, we will use the MATLAB/Simulink environment to simulate a three-phase asynchronous machine. The advantage of the MATLAB/Simulink environment is its ability to perform block modeling, which provides clarity and flexibility

in changing the model structure. Figure 6 shows the complete diagram of the proposed model of a three-phase asynchronous machine. This diagram includes both electrical equations and blocks describing the mechanical dynamics of the system. This model is comprehensive and allows for research that is as close as possible to real operating conditions.

Figure 6. Model of a three-phase asynchronous motor in MATLAB/Simulink environment

The main purpose of modeling is to verify the adequacy of the mathematical description of the machine and to analyze its transient processes. The input parameters for the model were the stator voltage, pole number, stator and rotor winding resistance, stator and rotor leakage inductance, and mutual inductance (see Table 7). Figures 7 and 8 show the characteristics of the transient process of the new two-speed motor obtained using a three-phase asynchronous machine model in the MATLAB/Simulink environment. As can be seen in Figure 7, the transition process of a two-speed motor during direct start from side $2p_1 = 4$ lasts in the time interval from $t = 0$ to $t \approx 0.4$ s with significant current fluctuations with an amplitude of about ± 452 A, which is 6.9 times higher than the rated current of the machine ($I \approx 64.7$) with a shaft load of $230 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$. In steady state, the machine develops a torque of 235 N at a speed of 1448 revolutions per minute.

As can be seen in Figure 8, the transition process of a two-speed motor during direct start from side $2p_2 = 8$ lasts in the time interval from $t = 0$ to $t \approx 0.14$ s with significant current fluctuations with an amplitude of about ± 260 A, which is 6.18 times higher than the rated current of the machine ($I \approx 43$) with a shaft load of $260 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$. In steady state, the machine develops a torque of $265 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}$ at a speed of 731 rpm. Experimental studies of the new 4A200L8/4U3 two-speed motor were conducted in the test laboratory of energy motors. The test bench consists of three main parts (Figure 9): 1 - control cabinet; 2 - load bench for engines from 22 kW to 45 kW; 3 - personal computer with specialized software (operator's workstation).

The DMG digital multimeter measures currents, voltages, and other electrical characteristics. The voltage level is set by a computer. The multimeter also measures the power consumed by the electric motor. The information from the multimeter is sent to the computer, to the "Test It!" program. The test bench has a built-in industrial controller that switches the relay-contactor equipment according to commands from the "Test It!" program. A 132 kW load motor controlled by frequency converters is used to load the electric motor under test. The braking energy is dissipated by resistors installed in the test bench. The load torque of the electric motor under test is set by a computer. Torque is measured by torque sensors connecting the shafts of the electric motor under test and the load motor. When the automatic electric motor test is started, a user-defined sequence of actions is performed to determine the parameters of the electric motor. During the complete test sequence, the insulation of the electric motor is checked while the electric motor is idling, during a short circuit (with the rotor locked), and during the start and operation of the electric motor under load. Repeating the experiments ensured the reliability of the experimental data, equal to 0.97 . Based on the results of processing the experimental data, the numerical characteristics of these parameters were determined, and the correctness of the theoretical conclusions was evaluated. The results of processing the experimental data are summarized in Table 8.

Table 7. Input parameters of an asynchronous motor for calculating transient processes in MATLAB/Simulink

Parameter	Value	
	$2p_1 = 4$	$2p_2 = 8$
Stator winding resistance, R_s, Ω	0.12	0.401
Rotor winding resistance, R_r, Ω	0.149	0.368
Stator leakage inductance, L_{ls}, mH	1.207	1.805
Rotor leakage inductance, L_{lr}, mH	1.307	2.3
Mutual inductance, L_m, mH	18.07	23.6

Figure 7. Characteristics of the transition process of a two-speed motor from the side of $2p_1 = 4$: (a) torque variation curve, (b) speed variation curve, and (c) current change curve

Figure 8. Characteristics of the transition process of a two-speed motor from the side of $2p_2 = 8$: (a) torque variation curve, (b) speed variation curve, and (c) current variation curve

Figure 9. Schematic diagram of the test bench

Table 8. Performance capability data

No	P_1 kW	U_1 V	I_1 A	P_{el1} W	$P_{st}+P_{mech}$ W	P_{el} W	P_g W	P_2 kW	η %	$\cos \varphi$	M N·m	n min ⁻¹	s %
from $p = 2$ side													
1	6.3	380	18	122	951.9	11	15	5.2	82.5	0.538	33	1497	0.2
2	14>6	380	27.6	287	951.9	69	34	13.2	90.8	0.801	84.7	1493	0.5
3	22.6	380	39.1	576	951.9	172	69	20.8	92.2	0.876	133.6	1488	0.8
4	27.7	380	46.9	832	951.9	263	100	25.6	92.3	0.895	164.4	1485	1.0
5	32.7	380	54.8	1133	951.9	372	136	30.1	92.1	0.903	193.7	1482	1.2
6	39.7	380	66.3	1661	951.9	563	199	36.3	91.5	0.906	234.7	1478	1.5
7	46.2	380	77.5	2267	951.9	782	271	41.9	90.8	0.903	271.9	1473	1.8
8	50.2	380	84.7	2707	951.9	941	324	45.3	90.2	0.899	294.6	1470	2.0
from $p = 4$ side													
1	2.9	380	18.3	401	430	4	21	2.0	69.9	0.236	25.4	748.5	0.2
2	6.0	380	20.1	483	430	26	25	5.1	84	0.456	64.8	746.3	0.5
3	11.1	380	25.2	763	430	101	40	9.8	88	0.67	126.1	742.5	1.0
4	15.9	380	31.6	1201	430	216	63	14.0	88	0.765	181.5	738.8	1.5
5	20.4	380	38.3	1767	430	366	92	17.7	87	0.806	230.6	735	2.0
6	23.3	380	43	2225	430	488	116	20.0	86	0.82	261.2	732.4	2.35
7	24.5	380	45	2434	430	543	127	20.9	85.6	0.824	273.4	731.3	2.5
8	28.1	380	51.4	3175	430	740	166	23.6	84	0.829	310.1	727.5	3.0

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown by experimental studies of the new 4A200L8/4U3 motor with $p_1 = 2$ pole pairs, the useful power reaches a value of $P_2 = 20$ kW at an efficiency of $\eta = 86\%$, $\cos \varphi = 0.82$, $I_1 = 43$ A at slip $s = 2.35\%$, and on the $p_2 = 4$ pole pair side, the motor can develop a power of $P_2 = 36$ kW at an efficiency of $\eta = 91.5\%$, $\cos \varphi = 0.906$, $I_1 = 66$ A at slip $s = 1.5\%$. Figure 10 shows the performance capabilities of the new two-speed motor from both poles, constructed based on the results of experimental studies. The results of experimental tests of mechanical characteristics are summarized in Table 9. The mechanical characteristics of the new two-speed engine are shown in Figure 11.

As can be seen in Figure 11, for both numbers of pole pairs, the mechanical characteristics have sufficient rigidity (nominal slips on the $2p_1$ side = $4s = 1.5$ and on the $2p_2$ side = $8s = 2.35\%$) and a smooth appearance. For research in industrial conditions, the new two-speed motor was installed in the drive of a two-shaft mixer of the VL-400-VRU type. Scientific and production association (SPA) of the mining enterprise Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Company JSC. A LeCroy WR 64Xi digital oscilloscope was used to measure the current curves in the phases on both poles, which allows the current change curves of all three phases to be recorded simultaneously (Figure 12). It should be noted that the currents of the phases on both sides of the poles had identical values and a strictly defined shift between the phases (Figure 13). This confirms the complete symmetry of the obtained PCW in relation to the power supply network. To assess the effectiveness of the developed PSW, a comparison was made between the experimental data of the two-speed

motor under study and the parameters of serially produced single-speed and two-speed motors of the same size, having identical rotation frequencies (see Table 10).

Table 9. Mechanical characteristics data

No	From $p = 2$ side		From $p = 4$ side	
	M^*	n, min^{-1}	M^*	n, min^{-1}
1	0	1500	0	750
2	0.7	1485	0.5	743
3	1	1478	1	732
4	2.1	1440	1.9	705
5	2.3	1398	2.1	675
6	2.2	1350	2.1	653
7	1.9	1275	2.1	600
8	1.7	1200	1.9	525
9	1.4	1050	1.8	450
10	1.2	900	1.7	375
11	1.1	750	1.6	300
12	1.1	600	1.6	225
13	1.0	450	1.6	150
14	0.9	150	1.5	75
15	0.9	0	1.3	0

Figure 10. Performance capabilities of the new two-speed motor: (a) from the $2p_1$ side = 4 poles and (b) from the $2p_2$ side = 8 poles

Figure 11. Mechanical characteristics of the new two-speed motor: (a) from the $2p_1$ side = 4 poles and (b) from the $2p_2$ side = 8 poles

Figure 12. Illustration of experimental testing at Almalyk Mining and Metallurgical Company JSC

Figure 13. Current curves in phases recorded using a LeCroy WR 64Xi digital oscilloscope

Table 10. Comparison of the parameters of the new two-speed engine with the parameters of existing machines

No	Parameter	UOM	New two-speed motor		Existing two-speed motor		Existing single-speed motors	
			4A200L8/4UZ $p=4$	4A200L8/4UZ $p=2$	4A200L8/4UZ $p=4$	4A200L8/4UZ $p=2$	4A200L8UZ $p=4$	4A200L4UZ $p=2$
1	Axle height	mm	200		200		200	200
2	Outer diameter of stator	mm	349		349		349	349
3	Inner diameter of stator	mm	238		250		250	238
4	Air gap	mm	0,70		0,50		0,50	0,70
5	Number of stator/rotor slots		48/38		72/58		72/58	48/38
6	Length of stator and rotor pack	mm	215		185		185	215
7	Net power	kW	20	36	20	28	22	45
8	Stator current	A	43	66	45	53	45	83
9	Efficiency	%	86	91.5	86	88	88.5	92
10	$\cos\varphi$		0.82	0.91	0.77	0.91	0.84	0.9
11	Slip	%	2.35	1,5				
12	Number of turns in phase		108	72	204	102	114	56
13	Mass of insulated wires of the stator winding	kg		16.6		16.1	13.8	19.5

5. CONCLUSION

The comparison showed that the new two-speed motor develops a useful power of 36 kW on the $p = 2$ side, which is 80%, and 20 kW on the $p=4$ side, which is 90.9% of the rated power of single-speed motors of the 4A200L4UZ and 4A200L8UZ types, respectively. In relation to the useful power of the two-speed motor of the 4A200L8/4UZ type, the power developed by the new two-speed motor on the $p = 2$ side exceeds it by 22.2% with equal power on the $p=4$ side, manufactured by the Yaroslavl Electric Machine Building Plant ELDIN. This indicates that the power of the new two-speed motor is as close as possible to the power of single-speed motors and greatly exceeds the power of the existing two-speed motor of the same size.

This indicates that motors with a single PCW on the stator achieve a significant increase in useful power and a more efficient use of the active part of the electric machine on the side with lower polarity. Thus, the results of experimental studies of the two-speed motor confirm the possibility of widespread introduction of such motors for energy and resource savings to replace single-speed motors for drives of mechanisms with intense operation, where both speeds of rotation are equivalent, and also show the advantage of the new two-speed pole-changing winding, the use of which improves the characteristics of the two-speed motor.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

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O : Writing - Original Draft

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Derived data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, [AZ], on request.

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